

1 HIV : TB co-infection presents danger to the developing world.

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7 Public health risks include a large population of HIV-1+ mTB-infected individuals. We measured total
8 transcription in the blood in humans with HIV-1 only or in humans with an active HIV-1 and mTB
9 co-infection to understand the largest changes in transcription associated with HIV-1 co-infection in
10 humans. In the blood, we found silencing of *CD69*, activation of *cMIP* and *CEBPA*, as well as changes in
11 immune effector state markers by expression of *Aldh3a2*.

12 GSE203261

13 GSE213850

14 GSE49760

15 GSE50834

16 Citations

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